

William Cockburn on scurvy (1696, 1706, 1736)

by Harri Hemilä

Early historically interesting discussions of scurvy.

Biographies

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/William_Cockburn_\(physician\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/William_Cockburn_(physician))

<https://history.rcp.ac.uk/inspiring-physicians/william-cockburn>

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ref:odnb/5777>

<https://www.westminster-abbey.org/abbey-commemorations/commemorations/william-cockburn>

[https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Dictionary_of_National_Biography,_1885-1900/Cockburn,_William_\(1669-1739\)](https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/Dictionary_of_National_Biography,_1885-1900/Cockburn,_William_(1669-1739))

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä.

William Cockburn's discussion of scurvy was cited in:

William Cockburn (1669–1739), who had been medical adviser to the fleet and physician to the Blue Squadron, successfully treated with fresh vegetables (cabbage, carrots, colewort, and turnips) 100 sailors with scurvy – “perfect moving skeletons” – put ashore at Torbay in 1695. Cockburn was so successful in 1701 in advising the Navy to buy lemons that their price at Billingsgate Market rose above 4 per chest. [p.317]

Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment. *Nutr Rev.* 2009;67:315-32.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19519673>

... In Cockburn, the Lords of the Admiralty found a physician who believed in simplifying and codifying medical methods with a view to developing new and certain cures. As Physician to the Blue Squadron he closely observed and kept a detailed account of the cases of sickness he encountered, following the Sydenham method. These observations, with his views on subjects like victualing, scurvy, the diet and lodging of seamen, fevers, diseases “nearer and under the line”, and chemical medicine, were published after his first year in the service in a book dedicated to the Lords of the Admiralty. Cockburn oriented all this work toward finding cures for the diseases incident to seamen. [p.22]

Cook HJ. Practical medicine and the British Armed Forces after the “Glorious Revolution”. *Med Hist.* 1990 Jan;34(1):1-26.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2405217>

William Cockburn (1697) who had held the post of physician to H.M. Fleet. He indulges in much incredible etiology, but says, “green trade, as they call it, keeps a crew free from scurvy,” and that “if ever any care is taken for the sick in the navy this must be chiefly considered,” but also that it is “a disease left without a remedy at sea.”

Stockman R. James Lind and Scurvy. *Edinb Med J.* 1926 Jun;33(6):329-350.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29648100>

in 1736, William Cockburn, an influential physician attached to the Fleet, had published a new edition of his *Sea Diseases*, in which he argued that scurvy attacked those who were idle; with greater physical effort, “digestion and nutrition were better performed”; the sailor's traditional victuals were quite adequate, though fresh vegetables were active in curing those already sick. The standard antiscorbutic medicine issued at sea in that period, on the recommendation of the College of Physicians, was “elixir of vitriol,” made up of sulfuric acid with added alcohol, sugar, and flavorings. [p.46]

“... The lazy and indolent, and those of a sedentary life are most subject to scurvy; those that are of a cheerful and contented disposition, are less liable to it, than others.” This, of course, is a repetition of the view of Cockburn, already quoted, who believed that physical activity assisted in digestion. “In the inactive, digestion is weak, yielding a gross chyle which is not easily converted into blood, and transpiration is diminished.” For Cockburn, the consequence of the excessive volume of circulating fluid was a rise in pressure that forced out the spots of extravasated blood seen on the back and legs of scorbutics, he had been a pioneer in attempts to explain biological effects in terms of Newtonian mechanics. [p.60-61]

Lind then tackled the problem of what antiscorbutics could be carried on long voyages, because fresh vegetables and citrus fruit would spoil so easily. The Admiralty had proposed dried spinach, which could be moistened and boiled in the sailor's food, but he thought that Cockburn had probably been correct in his assessment that this would not “restore the natural juices of the plant lost by evaporation, and, as he imagined, altered by a fermentation which they underwent in drying.” This seemed to be confirmed by the failure of dried herbs to help the Austrian Army wintering in Hungary. [p.63]

Carpenter KJ (1986) *The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C.* 1986, p.12.
<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>

1696 edition

An account of the nature, causes, symptoms, and cure of the distempers that are incident to seafaring people with observations on the diet of the sea-men in His Majesty's navy: illustrated with some remarkable instances of the sickness of the fleet during the last summer, historically related.

<https://name.umdl.umich.edu/A33550.0001.001>

<https://quod.lib.umich.edu/e/eebo/A33550.0001.001?view=toc>

<https://books.google.fi/books?id=cqFkAAAACAAJ>

Book review:

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rstl.1695.0081>

The Scurvy.

... the *Scurvy*; which p.9

appears first in *red spots*, which afterwards become *blue*, and then *black*, upon the *legs* and *other* parts, with an extraordinary *weakness*, and besides attended with a *redness*, *itching*, and *rotteness* of the *gums*, and a *looseness* of the *teeth*; their pulse all this while being very unequal, *i. e.* sometimes *weak*, and sometimes very *great*: and all these accompanied with a great many more severe symptoms singled out, and describ'd by *Riverius*, and our learned Doctor *Willis*; which, therefore, I shall forbear to enumerate, but especially since 'tis none of my design to write a Treatise of the *Scurvey*, but only to give such illustrations, as may be useful for understanding our Sea Sickesses, and helping us in their Cure.

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Observation XI.

George Manning, aged 27 years, of a bilious Constitution, and a thin habit of body, was taken, on board the *Elizabeth*, with an out-breaking of abundance of red spots upon his Legs and Arms; a great many of those upon his Legs became of an olive colour, yellow, blue, and black. p.150

'Tis evident from what I said before of the *Scurvy*, and as that is

really distinguished from the *Melancholia Hypochondriaca*; that the fretty, rarify'd, and disunited parts are to be made closer, and of a stricter cohesion: and thus the small parts of the blood, not being separated in so great a quantity, in the brain, by the perspiration, into the Intestines, &c. there can be no such feverish affecti- ons, faintings, quick and slow pulses eruption upon the skin, &c. as we see every day. Now this compact- ness and stricter cohesion, can only be acquired by such Medicins, that, by their *quantity*, or of their own nature, can give body to the blood, or make that more compact; which must be in a natural state, and produce every thing that is natural, so soon as it acquires this natural cohesion. Now, ashore, we have really great numbers of Medicins, that answer this design, which can produce wonderful effects, when given in time, and in a way that this view shews us. Those are all the Medicins, we call *temperate*, besides those that are Analeptical, and mostly prescrib'd in Hectick Fe- vers, into which this disease naturally runs, tho sooner when helpt on by the use of the common Antiscorbu- ticks.

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But at Sea, where all the victuals, that are for their nourishment, en- courage this sickness so much, and encrease it: and all the provisions of Medicins, that is made for our Sea- sicknesses, have no respect to that: I think it not unreasonable to acknow- ledge that disease not to be cur'd at Sea.

Yet I was willing to make the best I could of our Patients in Scurvies; and therefore, that the Medicins we have might have the better effect, and the Chyle, that's very often the best alterative, might be convey'd in its full force; I order'd him a Vomit of ʒss *Sal vitriol.* in ʒijj of *Oxymel* of *Squils*, to be encouraged with large draughts of thin Water-gruel; he

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vomited three times, and an abundance of nasty stuff: then I ordered him to take as little of his Beef or Pork, for his Meal, as possible; and rather to live upon Burgoo, or Watergruel; his ordinary Drink was Barly Decoction, to every quart whereof I ordered ℥ij of *Syr. de Alth.* to be added; and for Medicins, I prescrib'd him the following Electuary to be taken of thrice a day.

℞. Pulp. Passul. maj. ℥iij. Cons. fl. Cynosbat ℥ij. fl. Lujul. ℥iss. oc. 69 ppt. ℥iij. Syr. e Suc. *Limon.* q. s. ut f. Elect.

After these Medicins were taken for three weeks, which time he was very exact in following directions, he recovered apace, and came to his perfect health.

1706 edition

Sea diseases: or, a treatise of their nature, causes, and cure. Also, an essay on bleeding in fevers; shewing, the quantities of blood to be let, in any of their periods. *The Second Edition* Corrected and much improved.

<https://archive.org/details/b30519056/page/n3/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/bim_eighteenth-century_sea-diseases-or-a-trea_cockburn-william-md_1706

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/nn5h2hzq/items?canvas=5>

The Scurvy.

<https://archive.org/details/b30519056/page/12/mode/2up>

§ VII. The Scurvy appears with *red Spots* in the *Arms* and *Legs* especially, which *afterwards* turn *Black* and then *Blew*, there is an extraordinary *Weakness*, a *Redness*, *Itching* and *Rottenness* of the *Gums*, and a *Loosness* of the *Teeth*, their *Pulse* is very *unequal* i. e. sometimes *weak*, and sometimes very *great*, all these Symptoms are attended with a great many more not so constant, which are described at large by those that write particularly on this Subject; but cannot be properly spoke to here, since it is not so much my business to make a thorow enquiry into the Nature and Cure of that Disease, as it is to find the Causes, why it is so easily produced among Seamen, that they being sufficiently known, the hints here given may prove useful in the Curing and preventing that Distemper.

p.12

...

Dr. *Willis* has endeavoured to speak distinctly to the different kinds of Scurveys and calls one of them a Cold, and another of them a hot Scurvey; But in this contrary to Custome,¹ he has follow'd the Opinion of the Antients; and in this he embraces their Opinion when not so right, when in other cases he erroneously forsakes them, and the truth at the same time: For it is the last only

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1 James Lind also criticised Thomas Willis:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17226864>

of his Division that deserves the name, and the other does not really differ from the Melancholia Hypochondriaca. I may seem a little too Nice, and the dispute appear as if it lay only in a name, but what I have said before makes it evident, how useful it is to have proper descriptions of and names for things, and it is likewise manifest into what mistakes ambiguous expressions lead people; which are fatal in the Cure of Diseases.

Observation 15th of the Scurvy.

<https://archive.org/details/b30519056/page/212/mode/2up>

Observation XV.

George Manning, aged 27 years, of a bilious Constitution, and a thin habit of Body, was taken, on board the *Elizabeth*, with an out breaking of abundance of red spots upon his Legs and Arms; a great many of those upon his Legs became of an olive colour, yellow, blew, and black.

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It is evident, by what I have already said concerning the Scurvy, that the great design for curing it, must be to render the Blood so fluid that it may Circulate without those interruptions, by which it breaks some most tender and Capillarie Arteries, and runs out in a quantity the resistance of the place does allow. By those means, the extravasated Blood will be sooner transpired, and further extravasations be sufficiently prevented.

The feverish Heats, Ulcers, and inequality of the Pulse are no Contra-indications to this design: On the contrary, as they are Symptoms of this Disease, so they vanish likewise by this course; tho' proper Medicines may be given, at the same time, or mixt in with the other, whereby these Symptoms are made very tolerable while the

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main design is carrying on.

This Disease is particularly more Difficult to be cured at Sea; because their way of living, and their food rather encourage, than contribute, in the least, to its Cure. Nay, notwithstanding that the Scurvy is reputed the most common Distemper of the Sea, I do not find any provision made against it in the great Inventory of Sea-Medicins. And therefore where the hands of a Physician are tyed up for want of Tools, I cannot see what success can be expected in that Disease. I can only inform you of what I hinted before, that of all the number we meet with, Ill of the Scurvy, a fourth part of these do not contract it directly from a state of Health; but by beginning too soon upon their Sea Provisions after they recover of Fevers, or other Distempers: So that if sufficient care were taken about their coming upon their former Diet, they should not be so liable to have this Disease. At the same time, it is worthy our Observation how suddenly and how perfectly they recover of this Distemper ashoar, when they are free of this Diet, and only live upon Green Trade (as they call it) viz. Colewarts, Carrots, Cabbages, Turnips, &c. People put ashoar, in the most pitiful state that can be imagined, are able in three or four Days, by this food only, to walk several Miles into the Country. If ever any Care is taken for the sick in the Navy, this must be chiefly considered. But to return to our present sick Person, and that I may give you no further trouble of a sickness left without a remedy at Sea; which is almost as Melancholly as to consider these poor people at Sea, without a Rudder, I shall relate the Course I took with him in this straight, and difficulty.

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I was willing to make the best

I could of our Patients in Scurvies; and therefore, that the Medicins we have might produce the better effect, and the Chyle, that's very often the best Alterative, might be convey'd in its full force; I order'd him a Vomit of ... *Sal vitriol* in ... of *Oxymel* of *Squils*, to be encouraged with large draughts of thin Water-gruel; he Vomited three times, and an abundance of nasty stuff; then I ordered him to take as little of his Beef or Pork, for his Meal as possible; and rather to live upon Burgoo, or Water-gruel; his ordinary Drink was Barly Decoction, to every quart whereof I ordered ... of *Syr. de Alth.* to be added; and for Medicins, I prescrib'd him the following Electuary to be taken of thrice a day.

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R_x. ...

After these Medicins were taken for three weeks, which time he was very exact in following directions, he recovered apace, and came to his perfect health.

1736 edition

Sea diseases: or, a treatise of their nature, causes, and cure. Also an essay on bleeding in fevers; ...

The third edition, corrected and much improved

https://archive.org/details/bim_eighteenth-century_sea-diseases-or-a-trea_cockburn-w_1736/mode/2up

Preface.

https://archive.org/details/bim_eighteenth-century_sea-diseases-or-a-trea_cockburn-w_1736/page/n15/mode/2up

The *Scurvy* being generated by the Salt Provisions, altogether unavoidable at Sea, make one of the constant Diseases in Navies, and is the Reason why it seldom appears in Camps. On the contrary, the putting the Seamen ashore off of the mentioned Diet, proves their absolute Cure. This was very conspicuous in 1695, when we were to be one month in *Torbay*. I then persuaded my Lord *Berkeley* to have Tents made ashore for the Men that were most afflicted with that Distemper. His Lordship objected, that the Men would desert the Service, but after considering their being absolutely useless, he had Tents set up in the Bottom of the Bay, and above an hundred were put ashore, perfect moving Skeletons, scarcely able to get out of their Ships; they had fresh Provisions allowed them, with *Carrots*, *Turnips*, and other green Trade. In a Week they were able to crawl about, and, before the Fleet put to Sea, they returned to their Ships, not above two or three leaving the Service.

p.xvi-xvii

The Scurvy.

https://archive.org/details/bim_eighteenth-century_sea-diseases-or-a-trea_cockburn-w_1736/page/10/mode/2up

§.VII THE *Scurvy* appears with *red Spots* in the *Arms* and *Legs* especially, which *afterwards* turn *black* and then *blue*, there is an extraordinary *Weakness*, a *Redness*, *Itching*: and *Rottenness* of the *Gums*, and a *Looseness* of the *Teeth*, their *Pulse* is very *unequal*, *i. e.* sometimes *weak*, and sometimes very *great*; all these Symptoms are attended with a great many more not so constant, which are described at large by those that write particularly on this

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Subject, but cannot be properly spoke to here, since it is not so much my Business to make a thorough Enquiry into the *Nature* and *Cure* of that *Disease*, as it is to find the *Causes*, why it is so easily produced among *Seamen*, that they being sufficiently known, the Hints, here given, may prove; useful in the *curing* and *preventing* that Distemper.

Observation 15th of the Scurvy.

https://archive.org/details/bim_eighteenth-century_sea-diseases-or-a-trea_cockburn-w_1736/page/204/mode/2up

Observation XV.

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GEORGE MANNING, aged twenty-seven Years, of a *bilous* Constitution, and a thin Habit of Body, was taken, on Board the *Elizabeth*, with an Out-breaking of abundance of red Spots upon his Legs and Arms; a great many of those upon his Legs became of an *Olive* Colour, *yellow*, *blue*, and *black*.

It is evident, by what I have already said concerning the Scurvy, that the great Design for curing it, must be to render the Blood so fluid that it may circulate without those Interruptions, by which it breaks some most tender and *Capillary Arteries*, and runs out in a Quantity the Resistance of Place does allow. By those Means, the extravasated Blood will be sooner transpired, and further Extravasations be sufficiently prevented. The feverish Heats, Ulcers, and Inequality of the Pulse, are no Contra-Indications to this Design: On the contrary, as they are Symptoms of this Disease, so they vanish likewise by this Course; tho' proper Medicines may be given, at the same time, or mix'd in with the other, whereby these Symptoms are made very tolerable while the main Desing is carrying on.

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thin Water-gruel; he vomited three times, and an abundance of nasty Stuf: Then I order'd him to take as little of his *Beef* or *Pork*, for his Meal as possible; and rather to live upon Burgoo, or Water-gruel; his ordinary Drink was *Barley Decoction*, to every Quart whereof I order'd ... and for Medicines, I prescrib'd him the following Electuary to be taken of thrice a day.

R_x. ...

AFTER these Medicines were taken for three Weeks, which time he was very exact in following Directions, he recovered apace, and came to his perfect Health.